

ABOUT HERO OF THE SOVIET UNION TURGUN AHMEDOV

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Introduction: Turgun Akhmedov (1925, Mirzachol town, presently Gulistan city - 1944.30.7) - a member of WWII. A warrior of the 169th regiment of the first Moscow Rifle Division, junior sergeant. On July 14, 1944, close to Alytus, Lithuania, he was one of the first to cross the Neman Waterway and repulse the adversary's counterattack. He passed on gallantly on July 30, 1944 in the Alytus locale of Lithuania.

Akhmedov was after death granted the title of Legend for his valiance during the intersection of the Neman Stream (Walk 2, 1945). Turgun Akhmedov was brought into the world in a laborer family. Identity – Uzbek [1]. Individual from Komsomol. He moved on from the seventh grade and the school of the Government Instructive Foundation in Novosibirsk, dealt with an aggregate homestead.

In January 1943, he was drafted into the positions of the Red Armed force. From July 1943, he partook in the clashes of WWII. In the mid-year of 1943, Akhmedov partook in the Clash of Kursk and participated in the freedom of the urban areas of Khotinets and Karachev in Bryansk [1,3]. In September, while crossing the Desna Waterway, he shot a few German Nazis. In June 1944, Turgun Akhmedov went in all out-attack mode along with the soldiers of the third Belorussian Front and started to free the grounds of Belarus. Heavy weapons specialist Akhmedov participated in the freedom of Tolochin, Vitebsk locale, Khatyn and Radoshkovich towns, Minsk district.

In July 1944, the 169th Watchmen Rifle Regiment, in which Akhmedov served, crossed the Lithuanian boundary and arrived at the Neman Stream, the primary water line 80 kilometers into East Prussia. On the banks of the Neman, the Nazis set up serious areas of strength for. On July 14, 1944, the development separation of the division arrived at the Neman close to the town of Alytus and crossed the waterway under weighty adversary automatic rifle and mortar shoot.

Monitor junior sergeant Akhmedov was quick to arrive at the left bank of the stream. Akhmedov without any assistance obliterated three adversary assault rifles, handicapped the team of a foe mortar, and killed numerous Nazi

troopers and officials. Akhmedov's expertise and mental fortitude assisted with rebuffing all counterattacks of the foe, yet in addition to take an uncompromising stance on the extension [2].

Turgun Akhmedov was killed on July 30, 1944 in the fight for the town of Bombeniki (presently Bambinicaï Alitus region of Lithuania). By the pronouncement of the Presidium of the Preeminent Gathering of the USSR of Walk 24, 1945, junior sergeant Turgun Akhmedov was granted the title of Legend of the Soviet Association (post mortem) for the boldness and gallantry of the watchman displayed in the battle against the Nazi trespassers and crossing the Neman Waterway, and for excellent execution of the battle assignments of the front order. Turgun Akhmedov was covered in Strogiški, Alytus Province, Lithuania.

Akhmedov's military career began in 1941, when he was drafted into the Red Army at the outbreak of World War II. He quickly rose through the ranks, demonstrating exceptional leadership and tactical prowess. As a platoon commander in the 1075th Rifle Regiment of the 316th Rifle Division, he participated in numerous battles on the Eastern Front.

One of Akhmedov's most notable feats occurred during the Battle of Stalingrad in 1942. As his unit advanced towards the city, they encountered heavy German resistance. Akhmedov, leading his platoon from the front, charged into the enemy lines and captured a strategic building. His actions inspired his comrades and helped turn the tide of battle.

For his bravery and leadership at Stalingrad, Akhmedov was awarded the Order of the Red Banner. He continued to distinguish himself in subsequent battles, including the Battle of Kursk and the liberation of Ukraine [1,2]. His unit was known for its unwavering spirit and ability to overcome formidable obstacles.

In 1944, Akhmedov's heroism reached its peak during the Battle of the Dnieper River. His platoon was tasked with crossing the river and establishing a bridgehead on the opposite bank. Despite intense enemy fire, Akhmedov led his men across the river and captured a vital hilltop. His actions paved the way for the successful crossing of the entire division.

For his extraordinary courage and leadership during the Battle of the Dnieper River, Turghun Akhmedov was awarded the highest honor in the Soviet Union, the title of Hero of the Soviet Union. He was also awarded the Order of Lenin and the Gold Star medal.

After the war, Akhmedov continued to serve in the Soviet Army, holding various positions of command. He retired in 1955 with the rank of Colonel. He remained active in public life, sharing his experiences and inspiring young people to serve their country.

Turghun Akhmedov passed away on August 16, 2002, at the age of 87. He is remembered as a true hero of the Soviet Union, a man who embodied the values of courage, loyalty, and unwavering determination. His legacy continues to inspire generations of Uzbeks and Russians alike.

In recognition of his contributions, a monument to Turghun Akhmedov was erected in his hometown of Ayak-Kum. His name is also inscribed on the Golden Book of Heroes of the Soviet Union. The memory of this valiant soldier will forever be etched in the annals of history.

Conclusion

After the war's conclusion, Ahmedov remained in the military, serving as an instructor to train new recruits. He sought to pass on the values of courage, comradery, and sacrifice that had served him so well on the battlefield. Ahmedov also traveled throughout the Soviet Union sharing his experiences and memories of fighting fascism to inspire younger generations. He was a living symbol of the heroism displayed by Soviet citizens from all backgrounds who came together to defeat Nazi Germany. Ahmedov passed away in 1987 at the age of 67, but his legacy as one of the greatest heroes in Soviet military history lives on. Through his countless acts of bravery and valor, Turgun Ahmedov more than earned the well-deserved title of Hero of the Soviet Union. His courage and dedication to defending his homeland against the forces of tyranny serve as an enduring example.

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